

Technical Document

The Procedural Knowledge Ontology (PKO) for the PERKS Platform

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The PERKS platform provides an integrated environment for the management of procedural knowledge across its full lifecycle, from knowledge elicitation and extraction to validation, storage, exploitation, and auditing. Its reference architecture is organised around a set of interoperable solutions that address complementary needs in industrial contexts, where procedures are often distributed across heterogeneous sources, expressed in different formats, and maintained by different stakeholders.

At the centre of the platform, the Procedural Knowledge Management System (PKMS) acts as the common knowledge layer, storing procedures and related assets in a knowledge graph and providing uniform access to the other solutions. Automatic and manual extraction components support the acquisition of procedural knowledge from documents and expert input, while human-in-the-loop validation ensures that the resulting knowledge is checked and refined by domain experts before being made available for use. Auditing services provide traceability over both knowledge extraction and procedure execution, supporting accountability and continuous improvement. Finally, conversational interfaces enable end users to access and exploit procedural knowledge through natural language interaction, making the platform suitable for both expert users involved in knowledge management and operational users who need guidance during procedure execution.

Additional details on the PERKS Platform are available in project deliverables on Zenodo¹.

In the following sections, we will show by example how PKO has been used within the PERKS Platform for supporting all components.

Please note that these examples do not show all classes and properties included in the ontology. To have a complete view of the ontology, refer to the GitHub repository².

1 PREFIXES

This section lists the prefixes used in the following examples.

¹https://zenodo.org/communities/perks_project/records

²<https://github.com/perks-project/pk-ontology>

5 CHANGE OF STATUS

The resource `ex:example-loto/version-1.0` (figure 7) is linked to a status transition event through `pko:hasChangeOfStatus`, which points to a `pko:ChangeOfStatus` instance. This entity explicitly captures the evolution of the procedure's lifecycle, specifying that the status changed from `pko:Approved` to `pko:Deprecated` via the properties `pko:fromStatus` and `pko:toStatus`.

The transition is associated with the agent `ex:Jane-Doe` through `prov:wasAssociatedWith`, thus providing provenance information about who performed or triggered the change. Temporal information could also be added. Overall, this pattern enables the explicit representation of status evolution over time, supporting traceability and auditability of procedural knowledge.

Change of Status can also be applied to other entities, e.g., the procedure execution.

```
ex:example-loto/version-1.0 a pko:Procedure ;
  pko:hasChangeOfStatus [ a pko:ChangeOfStatus ;
    prov:wasAssociatedWith ex:Jane-Doe ;
    pko:fromStatus pko:Approved ;
    pko:toStatus pko:Deprecated ] .
```

Figure 7: Procedure change of status.